
Research Article

New names and new combinations in Orchidaceae of Africa and Americas

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Abstract: Nine new names and 70 new combinations are proposed here for 79 Orchid species of Africa and Americas belonging to 30 genera. These new names and new combinations are needed to comply with current taxonomic concepts of the respective genus.

Keywords: Angola, Bolivia, Brazil, Cameroon, Colombia, Costa Rica, Ecuador, Endemic, French Guiana, Gabon, Guatemala, Guyana, Mexico, Orchid, Panama, Peru, Sierra Leone, Venezuela

Introduction

The recent molecular and phylogenetic studies of the family Orchidaceae have changed the generic concept, delimitation and classification within the family. Based on the current, stable and wider generic circumscriptions in the family Orchidaceae (Pridgeon et al., 2003, 2009, 2014; Chase et al., 2015; Schuiteman & Chase 2015; Wilson et al., 2017; Vieira et al., 2024), nine new names and 70 new combinations are required for 79 Orchid species of Africa and Americas, belonging to 30 genera [*Andinia* (Luer) Luer, *Andreettaea* Luer, *Angraecum* Bory, *Aulosepalum* Garay, *Brassia* R.Br., *Comparettia* Poepp. & Endl., *Cyrtochilum* Kunth, *Deiregyne* Schltr., *Elleanthus* C.Presl, *Epidendrum* L., *Eulophia* R.Br., *Gomesa* R.Br., *Habenaria* Willd., *Laelia* Lindl., *Lycaste* Lindl., *Maxillaria* Ruiz & Pav., *Microchilus* C.Presl, *Oncidium* Sw., *Otoglossum* (Schltr.) Garay & Dunst., *Pelexia* Poit. ex Lindl., *Prosthechea* Knowles & Westc., *Pteroglossa* Schltr., *Pterostemma* Kraenzl., *Rossioglossum* (Schltr.) Garay & G.C.Kenn., *Sobralia* Ruiz & Pav., *Telipogon* Kunth, *Trichocentrum* Poepp. & Endl.,

Trichosalpinx Luer, *Zootrophion* Luer and *Zygostates* Lindl.], which are made here. We followed the guidelines and recommendations of Article 41 in Turland et al. (2018).

Nomenclature

Andinia medinae (Kolan. & Szlach.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Neooreophilus medinae* Kolan. & Szlach., *Diversity (Basel)* 14(5)-372: 20. 2022.

Holotype: Colombia, Putumayo, Vereda Balsayaco, near San Andres, 1984 m, 7 September 2016, *R. Medina T. S14/28* (JAUM).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Andreettaea antioquiensis (Sauleda, Uribe Vélez & Szlach.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Muscarella antioquiensis* Sauleda, Uribe Vélez & Szlach., *New World Orchid. Nomencl. Notes* 118: 1. 2023.

Holotype: Colombia, Antioquia, exact locality unknown, specimen made from cultivation in 2019, *J.L.A. Restrepo s.n.* (HPUJ).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Angraecum elzbietae (Mytnik, Szlach. & Olędrz.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Lesliegraecum elzbietae* Mytnik, Szlach. & Olędrz., *Nordic J. Bot.* 36(7)-e01692: 2. 2018.

Holotype: Madagascar, Toamasina province, Region of Aloatra Mangoro, Moramanga district, community of Ambohibary, Ampitabe village, Ambatovy mine, conservation zone of d'Ambatovy on ferruginous crust, Ampanatovana forest, 1085 m, 9 June 2008, *Antilahimena, Ratodimanana, Rotojoniaina, Ralaisabotsy & Felix 6278* (MO).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Madagascar.

Aulosepalum sahagunii (R.González & Lizb.Hern.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Gracielanthus sahagunii* R.González & Lizb.Hern., *Ibugana* 5: 64. 2013.

Holotype: Mexico, Jalisco, Municipio de Mazamitla, Puerto El Zapatero, 15 May 1995, *E. Sahagún s.n.* (IBUG).

Distribution: Endemic to United Mexican States.

Brassia colombiana (Sauleda & Uribe Vélez) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Brassiopsis colombiana* Sauleda & Uribe Vélez, *New World Orchid. Nomencl. Notes* 70: 6. 2020.

Holotype: Colombia, Risaralda, exact locality unknown, specimen made from cultivation in the collection

of Melfy Arrubla of Pereira, *Anon. s.n.* (HPUJ).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Comparettia bicornuta (Szlach., Kolan. & Oledrz.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Scelochilus bicornutus* Szlach., Kolan. & Oledrz., *Phyton* (Horn) 55(2): 305. 2015.

Holotype: Ecuador, Pichincha province, Volcan Pululagua, Quito-Calacali, 2000 m, December 1985, *Hirtz 2182* (RPSC).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Ecuador.

Comparettia bolivariensis (Szlach., Kolan. & Oledrz.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Scelochilus bolivariensis* Szlach., Kolan. & Oledrz., *Phyton* (Horn) 55(2): 299. 2015.

Holotype: Ecuador, Bolivar province, Guaranda-Caluma-Catarama, near Pasagua at 25.3 km, 875 m, 5 July 1991, *Dodson et al. 18776* (RPSC).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Ecuador.

Comparettia colombiana (Uribe Vélez & Sauleda) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Scelochilus colombianum* Uribe Vélez & Sauleda, *New World Orchid. Nomencl. Notes* 63: 2. 2020.

Holotype: Colombia, Cauca, from La Bota Caucana, near the headwaters of the Caqueta River, 2018, *J.L. Aguirre s.n.* (HJPU).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Comparettia denticulata (Szlach., Kolan. & Oledrz.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Scelochilus denticulatus* Garay ex Szlach., Kolan. & Oledrz., *Phyton* (Horn) 55(2): 301. 2015.

Holotype: Ecuador, Tungurahua province, Rio Topo, Banos-Puyo, 1300 m, June 1983, *Hirtz 987* (RPSC).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Ecuador.

Comparettia obovata (Szlach., Kolan. & Oledrz.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Scelochilus obovatus* Szlach., Kolan. & Oledrz., *Phyton* (Horn) 55(2): 303. 2015.

Holotype: Ecuador, Cotopaxi province, 52 km Quevedo to Latacunga at Tene fuerte, 900 m, 20 June 1987, *Hirtz 17197* (RPSC).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Ecuador.

Comparettia pseudochiribogae (Szlach., Kolan. & Oledrz.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Scelochilus pseudochiribogae* Szlach., Kolan. & Oledrz., *Phyton (Horn)* 55(2): 303. 2015.

Holotype: Ecuador, Pichincha province, west and above Tandapi, 1750 m, 31 March 1985, *Luer et al.* 11023 (RPSC).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Ecuador.

Comparettia pubescens (Szlach., Kolan. & Oledrz.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Scelochilus pubescens* Szlach., Kolan. & Oledrz., *Phyton (Horn)* 55(2): 305. 2015.

Holotype: Ecuador, Tungurahua province, Mt. Tungurahua, 2500 m, 20 January 1990, *Hirtz et al.* 4532 (RPSC).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Ecuador.

Comparettia schmidt-mummii (Szlach. & Kolan.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Scelochilus schmidt-mummii* Szlach. & Kolan., *Syst. Bot.* 40(1): 96. 2015.

Holotype: Colombia, Cundinamarca, Guayabetal, Monteredondo, 1700 m, 16 June 1961, *H. Schmidt-Mumm* 85 (COL).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Comparettia solomonii (Szlach., Kolan. & Oledrz.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Scelochilus solomonii* Szlach., Kolan. & Oledrz., *Phyton (Horn)* 55(2): 307. 2015.

Holotype: Bolivia, La Paz, Nor Yungas province, 14.3 km southwest (above) of Yolosa on road to Chuspipata, 2000 m, 10 March 1984, *Solomon & Stein* 11746 (MO).

Distribution: Plurinational State of Bolivia and Republic of Peru.

Comparettia tandayapensis (Szlach., Kolan. & Oledrz.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Scelochilus tandayapensis* Szlach., Kolan. & Oledrz., *Phyton (Horn)* 55(2): 301. 2015.

Holotype: Ecuador, Pichincha province, Tandayapa on road Nono to Nanegal, 1800 m, December 1984, *Hirtz* 2179 (RPSC).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Ecuador.

Cyrochilum antioquiaensis (Uribe Vélez, Saulea & Szlach.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Dasyglossum antioquiaensis* Uribe Vélez, Saulea & Szlach., *New World Orchid. Nomencl. Notes* 91: 1. 2020.

Holotype: Colombia, Antioquia, eastern slope of the central mountain range, 2 100 m, 2019, specimen made from cultivation, *J.L. Aguirre s.n.* (HPUJ).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Cyrtochilum caucanum (Uribe Vélez, Sauleda & Szlach.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Dasyglossum caucanum* Uribe Vélez, Sauleda & Szlach., New World Orchid. Nomencl. Notes 81: 2. 2020.

Holotype: Colombia, Cauca, from La Bota Caucana, near the headwaters of the Caqueta River, 2700 m, specimen made from cultivation in 2019, *Jose Luis Aguirre s.n.* (HPUJ).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Cyrtochilum putumayoensis (Uribe Vélez, Sauleda & Szlach.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Dasyglossum putumayoensis* Uribe Vélez, Sauleda & Szlach., New World Orchid. Nomencl. Notes 93: 1. 2021.

Holotype: Colombia, Putumayo, near Mocoa, 2019, *J.C. Ordonez s.n.* (HPUJ).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Cyrtochilum szlachetkoi R.Kr.Singh, *nom. nov.*

≡ *Trigonochilum koenigeri* Szlach., Kolan. & Chiron, Bot. Stud. (Taipei) 58-8: 23. 2017.

Holotype: Colombia, Putumayo, Valle de Sibundoy, Vereda San Pablo Bajo en km 3 lado izquierdo de la carretera, specimen made from cultivation, *R. Medina 325* (MEDEL).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Etymology: Named after Dr. Dariusz Lucjan Szlachetko, Orchidologist.

Notes: The species epithet *koenigeri* is preoccupied in the genus *Cyrtochilum* Kunth [*Cyrtochilum koenigeri* Szlach. & Kolan., PeerJ 8(e8566): 133. 2020], therefore, a new name is herein proposed.

Deiregyne xochitliae (R.González & Lizb.Hern.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Triceratostris xochitliae* R.González & Lizb.Hern., Ibugana 5: 67. 2013.

Holotype: Mexico, Zacatecas, Municipio de Juchipila, Sierra de Morones, 4.5 km camino Juchipila-Pueblo Viejo, 1900 m, 16 March 2007, *X. Cuevas, L. Hdez. & J.A. Pérez s.n.* (IBUG).

Distribution: Endemic to United Mexican States.

Elleanthus garayanus (Szlach., Dudek & S.Nowak) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Evelyna garayana* Szlach., Dudek & S.Nowak, Mater. Orchid Fl. Colombia 4: 3 31. 2023.

Holotype: Ecuador, Bei der Hacienda Pinca im Thal von Peruden an Rio Grallabanks bei Quito, 2000 m, 3 January 1880, *F.C. Lehmann 429* (W).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Ecuador.

Elleanthus lojtnantianus (Szlach. & Dudek) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Adeneleuterophora lojtnantiana* Szlach. & Dudek, Mater. Orchid Fl. Colombia 4: 341. 2023.

Holotype: Costa Rica, without locality, *A. Endres s.n.* (W).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Costa Rica.

Elleanthus szlachetkoi R.Kr.Singh, *nom. nov.*

≡ *Evelyna lindenii* Szlach., Dudek & S.Nowak, Mater. Orchid Fl. Colombia 4: 330. 2023, *nom. illeg., non* Rchb.f., Bot. Zeitung (Berlin) 10: 709. 1852.

Holotype: Venezuela, Mérida, July 1846, *J.J. Linden 1217* (W).

Distribution: Endemic to Bolivarian Republic of Venezuela.

Etymology: Named after Dr. Dariusz Lucjan Szlachetko, Orchidologist.

Epidendrum colombiensis R.Kr.Singh, *nom. nov.*

≡ *Takulumena garayi* Kolan. & Szlach., Phytol. (Horn) 61: 22. 2021.

Holotype: Colombia, Cauca, between Coconuco and Paletará, 29 July 1961, *L.A. Garay et al.* 326 (AMES).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Etymology: The species is named after Colombia, the country from which it was discovered.

Notes: The species epithet *garayi* is preoccupied in the genus *Epidendrum* L. (*Epidendrum garayi* Lojtnant, Bot. Not. 130: 325. 1977), therefore, a new name is herein proposed.

Eulophia bamendensis (Szlach.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Cyrtopera bamendensis* Szlach., Orchid. W.-Centr. Africa 3: 91. 2021.

Holotype: Cameroon, Bamenda, Nchan, *Maitland 1753* (P).

Distribution: Endemic to Cameroon.

Eulophia cristatofimbriata (Szlach.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Orthochilus cristatofimbriatus* Szlach., Orchid. W.-Centr. Africa 3: 31. 2021.

Holotype: Angola, *Baum 564* (HBG).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Angola.

Eulophia distans (Summerh.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Pteroglossaspis distans* Summerh., Kew Bull. 13(1): 82. 1958. *Orthochilus distans* (Summerh.)
Bytebier, Taxon 63(1): 18. 2014.

Holotype: Sierra Leone, Bonthe district, Taigbe, southeast of Bendu, in grassland on poor very sandy soil, 15 October 1946, *P. Adames 92* (K000306603!).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Sierra Leone.

Gomesa alvarenguensis (Campacci) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Coppensia alvarenguensis* Campacci, Colet. Orquídeas Brasil. 16: 659. 2020.

Holotype: Brazil, Minas Gerais, Alvarenga, 3510 ft, June 2013, *R. de Vasconcelos Leitão* (ESA).

Distribution: Endemic to Federative Republic of Brazil.

Gomesa ourobranquensis (Campacci) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Coppensia ourobranquensis* Campacci, Colet. Orquídeas Brasil. 17: 682. 2021.

Holotype: Brazil, Minas Gerais, Ouro Branco, 1450 m, August 2005, *P.M. Borges* (ESA).

Distribution: Endemic to Federative Republic of Brazil.

Habenaria echeverryi (Szlach. & Kolan.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Rhinorchis echeverryi* Szlach. & Kolan., Mater. Orchid Fl. Colombia 1: 221. 2017.

Holotype: Colombia, Vaupés, vicinity of Mitú, Rio Cuduyari, 200–250 m, 3 October 1991, *J. Kress, J. Betancur, C.S. Roesel & B. Echeverry 91-3369* (COL).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Habenaria fassetii (Szlach. & Kolan.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Rhinorchis fassetii* Szlach. & Kolan., Mater. Orchid Fl. Colombia 1: 220. 2017.

Holotype: Colombia, Santander, Valley of Quebrada Chima, Mountains west of Chima, 2300 m, 1 August 1944, *N.C. Fasset 25562* (US).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Habenaria heteroplectron (Rchb.f. ex Szlach. & Kolan.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Rhinorchis heteroplectron* Rchb.f. ex Szlach. & Kolan., Polish Bot. J. 59(2): 194. 2014.

Holotype: French Guiana, *Leprieur s.n.* (W).

Distribution: Endemic to French Guiana.

Habenaria luerorum (Szlach. & Kolan.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Rhinorchis luerorum* Szlach. & Kolan., Mater. Orchid Fl. Colombia 1: 222. 2017.

Holotype: Colombia, Antioquia, Raton Pelado, above Yaramal, 2650 m, 1 May 1984, *C.Luer, J. Luer, R. Escobar & E. Valencia 10048* (MO).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Habenaria pseudoplatycoryne (Szlach. & Olszewski) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Renzorchis pseudoplatycoryne* Szlach. & Olszewski, Adansonia sér. 3, 20(2): 326. 1998.

Holotype: Gabon, *Thollon s.n.* (P).

Distribution: Endemic to Gabonese Republic.

Habenaria santa-martae (Szlach. & Kolan.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Habenella santa-martae* Szlach. & Kolan., Mater. Orchid Fl. Colombia 1: 93. 2017.

Holotype: Colombia, Sierra Nevada de Santa Marta, above Finca Reflejo, Quebrada La Sirena, 1500–1800 m, 6 September 1972, *J.H. Kirkbride 2112* (COL).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Laelia degranvillei (Szlach., S.Nowak & Baranow) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Schomburgkia degranvillei* Szlach., S.Nowak & Baranow, Orchids Guianas 416. 2017.

Holotype: French Guiana, Roche Jutou, Bassin du Haut-Marouni, Pied de la Face S de la roche, 320 m, 16 August 1987, *de Granville, Allorge, Hahn & Hoff 9317* (MO).

Distribution: Endemic to French Guiana.

Lycaste fernandezii (Archila) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Selbyana fernandezii* Archila, Revista Guatemalensis 13(1): 96. 2010.

Holotype: Guatemala, Río Chixoy, 450 m, April 1997, *F. Archila FA-934* (BIGU).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Guatemala.

Lycaste hemileia (Archila) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Selbyana hemileia* Archila, *Revista Guatemalensis* 13(1): 99. 2010.

Holotype: Guatemala, Río Chixoy, June 1999, *F. Archila* FA-753 (BIGU).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Guatemala.

Lycaste velizii (Archila) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Selbyana velizii* Archila, *Revista Guatemalensis* 13(1): 110. 2010.

Holotype: Guatemala, Najquitob, 700 m, April 1990, *F. Archila* FA-781 (BIGU).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Guatemala.

Maxillaria anthropophora (Szlach. & Kolan.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Xanthoxerampellia anthropophora* Szlach. & Kolan., *Wulfenia* 24: 200. 2017.

Holotype: Colombia, Antioquia, Mpio, Urrao, Vereda Calles Abajo, Parque Nacional Natural Las Orquídeas, sector Venados, 1196 m, 30 July 2011, *R. Arevalo et al.* 930 (COL).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Maxillaria antonellii (O.Pérez & Bogarín) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Camaridium antonellii* O.Pérez & Bogarín, *Lankesteriana* 21(3): 352. 2021.

Holotype: Colombia, Valle del Cauca, El Cairo municipality, Cerro El Inglés, 'Santicos' locality, 2330 m, 25 March 2018, *O. Pérez-Escobar & A. Zuluaga* 1987 (CUVC).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Maxillaria blancoi R.Kr.Singh, *nom. nov.*

≡ *Rhetinantha whittenii* Szlach., Oledrz. & Lipinska, *Wulfenia* 27: 62. 2020.

Holotype: Colombia, Chocó, 24 July 1973, *J. White & R. Warner* 43 (AMES).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Etymology: Named after Dr. Mario Alberto Blanco, Costa Rican Botanist.

Notes: The species epithet *whittenii* is preoccupied in the genus *Maxillaria* Ruiz & Pav. [*Maxillaria whittenii* Dodson, *Orquideologia* 19(3): 89. 1994], therefore, a new name is herein proposed.

Maxillaria ecallosa (Lipinska & Szlach.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Christensonella ecallosa* Lipińska & Szlach., *Nordic J. Bot.* 35(1): 25. 2016.

Holotype: Brazil, Amazonia, Rio Negro, 16 October 1971, *Prance et al.* 15331 (US).

Distribution: Co-operative Republic of Guyana and Federative Republic of Brazil.

Maxillaria kolanowskae R.Kr.Singh, *nom. nov.*

≡ *Xanthoxerampellia betancurii* Szlach. & Kolan., *Wulfenia* 24: 201. 2017.

Holotype: Colombia, Antioquia, Mpio, Urrao, Corregimiento La Encarnación, Vereda Calles, camino Calles-La Encarnación, Parque Nacional Natural Las Orquídeas, despues de la confluencia del Rio Polo al Rio Calles y antes del Rio San Pedro, Sitio La Queibra, 1600–1850 m, 2 February 2011, *Betancur et al.* 14885 (COL).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Etymology: Named after Dr. Marta Kolanowska, Orchidologist.

Notes: The species epithet *betancurii* is preoccupied in the genus *Maxillaria* Ruiz & Pav. (*Maxillaria betancurii* Christenson, *Maxillaria Monogr.* 1: 114. 2013), therefore, a new name is herein proposed.

Maxillaria mercedes-abarcae (Vélez-Abarca & M.M.Jiménez) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Pityphyllum mercedes-abarcae* Vélez-Abarca & M.M.Jiménez, *Lankesteriana* 21(3): 290. 2021.

Holotype: Ecuador, Zamora Chinchipe, Cordillera del Cóndor flank, 1280 m, specimen made from cultivation on 24 September 2020, *L. Vélez LV0068* (ECUAMZ).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Ecuador.

Maxillaria monikae R.Kr.Singh, *nom. nov.*

≡ *Rhetinantha vallecaucana* Szlach., Oledrz. & Lipinska; *Phyton* (Horn) 59(1-2): 52. 2019.

Holotype: Colombia, Valle del Cauca, *Pennell & Killip 5864* (AMES-47368).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Etymology: Named after Dr. Monika Lipińska, Orchidologist.

Notes: The species epithet *vallecaucana* is preoccupied in the genus *Maxillaria* Ruiz & Pav. [*Maxillaria vallecaucana* (Kolan., Lipińska & Szlach.) J.M.H.Shaw, *Orchid Rev. Suppl.*, 127(1326): 45. 2019], therefore, a new name is herein proposed.

Maxillaria oledrzynskae R.Kr.Singh, *nom. nov.*

≡ *Rhetinantha peruviana* Szlach., Oledrz. & Lipińska, *Phyton* (Horn) 59(1-2): 50. 2019.

Holotype: Peru, Amazonas, 5 February 1964, *P.C. Hutchison & J.K. Wright 4083* (AMES).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Peru.

Etymology: Named after Dr. Natalia Olędrzyńska, Orchidologist.

Notes: The species epithet *peruviana* is preoccupied in the genus *Maxillaria* Ruiz & Pav. [*Maxillaria peruviana* (C.Schweinf.) D.E.Benn. & Christenson, Icon. Orchid. Peruvianum t. 510. 1998], therefore, a new name is herein proposed.

Maxillaria prostrata (Bogarín, Serracín & Samudio) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Maxillariella prostrata* Bogarín, Serracín & Samudio, Brittonia 70(4): 394. 2018.

Holotype: Costa Rica, Puntarenas, Coto Brus, San Vito, specimen made from cultivation on 27 October 2005, *D. Bogarín 2131* (JBL).

Distribution: Republic of Costa Rica and Republic of Panama.

Maxillaria sahuayacoensis R.Kr.Singh, *nom. nov.*

≡ *Sauvetea schweinfurthiana* Szlach. & Lipinska; Turkish J. Bot. 44(1): 94. 2020.

Holotype: Peru, Cuzco, La Convención province, Sahuayaco, 1600 m, 17 January 1947, *C. Vargas C. 6300* (AMES).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Peru.

Etymology: The new name is named after the type locality Sahuayaco.

Notes: The species epithet *schweinfurthiana* is preoccupied in the genus *Maxillaria* Ruiz & Pav. [*Maxillaria schweinfurthiana* (Garay & M.Wirth) Molinari, Richardiana 15: 299. 2015], therefore, a new name is herein proposed.

Maxillaria schneideri (Szlach., Oledrz. & Lipinska) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Rhetinantha schneideri* Szlach., Oledrz. & Lipinska, Phytion (Horn) 59(1-2): 50. 2019.

Holotype: Colombia, Cundinamarca, *Schneider 329* (AMES).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Maxillaria uribei (Szlach., Oledrz. & Lipinska) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Rhetinantha uribei* Szlach., Oledrz. & Lipinska; Wulfenia 27: 60. 2020.

Holotype: Colombia, Cundinamarca, *L. Uribe Uribe 5497* (COL-103045).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Microchilus epidendroides (Christenson ex Szlach.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Platythelys epidendroides* Christenson ex Szlach., Mater. Orchid Fl. Colombia 1: 37 4. 2017.

Holotype: Panama, Chiriquí, Quebrada Bonito and east of road, north of reservoir, Fortuna Dam area, 1100 m, 30 July 1984, W.G. D'Arcy, H.W. Churchill & C. Todzia 15888 (MO).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Panama.

Oncidium gerhardianum (Dalström & Deburghgr.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Odontoglossum gerhardianum* Dalström & Deburghgr., OrchideenJ. 26(1): 9. 2019.

Holotype: Bolivia, La Paz, exact locality unknown, M. Bang 1801 (BM).

Distribution: Endemic to Plurinational State of Bolivia.

Oncidium morae (Uribe Vélez, Sauleda & Szlach.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Odontoglossum morae* Uribe Vélez, Sauleda & Szlach., New World Orchid. Nomencl. Notes 106: 1. 2022.

Holotype: Colombia, Putumayo, near San Francisco, exact locality unknown, specimen made in February 2022 from a plant in cultivation in the collection of Maria Cristina Mora of Bogota (HPUJ).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Oncidium paniculatum (Dalström & Deburghgr.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Odontoglossum paniculatum* Dalström & Deburghgr., OrchideenJ. 25(4): 141. 2018.

Holotype: Ecuador, Sucumbios, La Bonita, 1800–2000 m, 29 March 1992, S. Dalström & J. Del Hierro 2066 (SEL).

Distribution: Republic of Colombia and Republic of Ecuador.

Oncidium universitas-lodziensis (Kolan., S.Nowak & Szlach.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Heteranthocidium universitas-lodziensis* Kolan., S.Nowak & Szlach., Phytion (Horn) 59(1-2): 45. 2019.

Holotype: Ecuador, Morona-Santiago, Domono, 1350 m, 18 November 1995, L. Suin 17 (HA).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Ecuador.

Oncidium × luerorum (Dalström & W.E.Higgins) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Odontoglossum × luerorum* Dalström & W.E.Higgins, Lankesteriana 19(1): 17. 2019.

Holotype: Ecuador, Carchi, epiphytic in cloud forest above Maldonado west of Tulcan, 2000–2500 m, 25 August 1978, C. Luer, J. Luer & A. Hirtz 3373 (SEL).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Ecuador.

Hybrid parents: *Oncidium mirandum* (Rchb.f.) M.W.Chase & N.H.Williams [≡ *Odontoglossum mirandum* Rchb.f.] × *Oncidium armatum* (Rchb.f.) M.W.Chase & N.H.Williams [≡ *Odontoglossum armatum* Rchb.f.].

Otoglossum cuencae (Kolan., Szlach. & Olędrz.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Ecuadorella cuencae* Kolan., Szlach. & Olędrz., *Wulfenia* 25: 111. 2018.

Holotype: Ecuador, Morona-Santiago, east of pass on road Cuenca to Limón, 2400 m, 20 November 1989, C. Dodson, N. Williams, E. Hagsater & M. Whitten 17733 (RPSC).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Ecuador.

Otoglossum stacyi (Kolan., Szlach. & Olędrz.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Ecuadorella stacyi* Kolan., Szlach. & Olędrz., *Wulfenia* 25: 114. 2018.

Holotype: Ecuador, J.E. Stacy s.n. (AMES).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Ecuador.

Pelexia laurensis (C.M.Martín & Szlach.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Pachygenium laurensis* C.M.Martín & Szlach., *PeerJ* 10(e13433): 10. 2022.

Holotype: Argentina, Jujuy, San Pedro, San Juan de Dios, Estancia Las Lauras, 906 m, 3 September 2020, C.M. Martín 2814 (JUA).

Distribution: Endemic to Argentine Republic.

Pelexia muyscara (Rinc.-González, Fonseca-Cortés & Salazar) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Pachygenium muyscarum* Rinc.-González, Fonseca-Cortés & Salazar, *Lankesteriana* 23(1): 98. 2023.

Holotype: Colombia, Cundinamarca, Bogotá D.C., Ciudad Bolívar, Arborizadora Alta, Cerro Seco, 2800 m, 15 July 2021, M. Rincón-González, A.I. Díaz & M. Pinzón 1842 (JBB).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Pelexia xerophytica (Szlach. & Kolan.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Pachygenium xerophyticum* Szlach. & Kolan., *Mater. Orchid Fl. Colombia* 2: 325. 2019.

Holotype: Colombia, Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 22 June 1972, R. Schnetter 494 (COL).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Prosthechea minima (Sauleda & Uribe Vélez) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Anacheilium minimum* Sauleda & Uribe Vélez, New World Orchid. Nomencl. Notes 107: 2. 2022.

Holotype: Colombia, Caqueta, road between Altamira and Florencia at El Portico, 1900–2000 m, specimen made from cultivation in the collection of J.L. Aguirre on 4 March 2022 (HPJU).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Prosthechea pseudocochleata (Szlach. & Kolan.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Anacheilium pseudocochleatum* Szlach. & Kolan., Mater. Orchid Fl. Colombia 4: 407. 2023.

Holotype: Colombia, C. Parra O. & B.V. Rodriguez 754 (COL).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Pteroglossa pignalii (Szlach., Baranow & S.Nowak) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Callistanthos pignalii* Szlach., Baranow & S.Nowak, Phytion (Horn) 57(1-2): 7. 2017.

Holotype: Brazil, Bahia, Praia do Forte, 13 September 1992, M. Pignal 425 (P00070034!).

Distribution: Endemic to Federative Republic of Brazil.

Pterostemma dodsoniana (Szlach. & Kolan.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Hirtzia dodsoniana* Szlach. & Kolan., Ann. Bot. Fenn. 52(3-4): 251. 2015.

Holotype: Peru, Pasco, Oxapampa, 53 km on road between Oxapampa & Paucartambo, 1950 m, 10 May 1992, D.N. Smith & A. Pretel 1483 (MO).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Peru.

Rossioglossum parvulum (Archila, Szlach. & Chiron) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Chelyorchis parvula* Archila, Szlach. & Chiron, Richardiana 16: 220. 2016.

Holotype: Guatemala, Alta Verapaz, camino a la repressa de Chixoy, 400 m, March 2009, F. Archila FA s.n. (BIGU).

Distribution: Endemic to Endemic to Republic of Guatemala.

Sobralia floribunda (Rchb.f. ex Baranow, Dudek & Szlach.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Brasolia floribunda* Rchb.f. ex Baranow, Dudek & Szlach., Pl. Syst. Evol. 303(7): 868. 2017.

Holotype: Colombia, without locality, Carden s.n. (W19190).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Sobralia linearistelidia (Baranow & Szlach.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Brasolia linearistelidia* Baranow & Szlach., Mater. Orchid Fl. Colombia 3: 200. 2020.

Holotype: Colombia, Santander, Mpio, San Vicente de Chucuri, Vereda El Centro, predio Junin, Camino de Longerke entre San Vincence y Zapatoca, PNN Serrania de Los Yariguies, 2200–2400 m, 20 August 2010, *E.Y. Rodriguez 1681* (COL-552175).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Sobralia magnistelidia (Baranow & Szlach.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Brasolia magnistelidia* Baranow & Szlach., Mater. Orchid Fl. Colombia 3: 205. 2020.

Holotype: Colombia, Cundinamarca, Pipulquer, *F.C. Lehmann BT 50* (AMES).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Telipogon boyacaense (Szlach. & Kolan.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Stellilabium boyacaense* Szlach. & Kolan., Wulfenia 23: 33. 2016.

Holotype: Colombia, Boyacá, Mpio, Miraflores-San Bernardo, Vereda Cardozo, 27 December 1984, *P. Bernal s.n.* (COL).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Telipogon colombianum (Szlach. & Kolan.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Stellilabium colombianum* Szlach. & Kolan., Wulfenia 25: 174. 2018.

Holotype: Colombia, Santander, Mpio, Gambita, Corregimiento del Taladro, Alto del Gaque, 1900 m, 5 March 1981, *S. Diaz 2294* (COL).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Telipogon fernandezii (Szlach. & Kolan.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Stellilabium fernandezii* Szlach. & Kolan., Wulfenia 23: 31. 2016.

Holotype: Colombia, Risaralda, Mpio, Mistrató, En la via San Antonio de Chami y Mistrató, Sitio Las Partidas, 1700 m, 6 April 1992, *J.L. Fernandez & Estud. Sist. Vegetal. 10133* (COL).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Telipogon valdiviesoanum (Kolan. & Medina Tr.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Stellilabium valdiviesoanum* Kolan. & Medina Tr., Polish Bot. J. 61(1): 20. 2016.

Holotype: Colombia, Putumayo, lower part of the village La Cumbre, 2150 m, 1 March 2014, *R. Medina T. 186* (MEDEL).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Trichocentrum juncifolium (L.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Epidendrum juncifolium* L., Sp. Pl., ed. 2. 2: 1351. 1763. *Cymbidium juncifolium* (L.) Willd., Sp. Pl., ed. 4 [Willdenow] 4(1): 102. 1805. *Oncidium juncifolium* (L.) Lindl., Coll. Bot. (Lindley) sub t. 27. 1821. *Cohniella juncifolia* (L.) Cetzal & Carnevali, Syst. Bot. 38(3): 614. 2013.

Lectotype: "Epidendrum foliis radicalibus subulatis" Plum. in Burm., Pl. Amer., t. 184, f. 2. 1758.

Distribution: Antigua and Barbuda, Dominica, Guadeloupe, Martinique and Saint Lucia.

Trichocentrum quichense (Coxic, Cetzal, E.Mó & Carnevali) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Lophiaris quichensis* Coxic, Cetzal, E.Mó & Carnevali, Phytotaxa 456(1): 65. 2020.

Holotype: Guatemala, Quiché, Chicamán, El Pinal, Cuenca Chixoy, 1042 m, *C.J. Zacarías-Coxic 1* (BIGU).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Guatemala.

Trichosalpinx bihuae (Monteros & Baquero) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Pseudolepanthes bihuae* Monteros & Baquero, Lankesteriana 21(1): 5. 2021.

Holotype: Ecuador, Carchi, Reserva Dracula, 2042 m, 29 January 2019, *M. Monteros 203* (QCNE).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Ecuador.

Zootrophion sauledae R.Kr.Singh, *nom. nov.*

≡ *Epibator mejiae* Sauleda, Uribe Vélez & Szlach., New World Orchid. Nomencl. Notes 117: 2. 2023.

Holotype: Colombia, Department of Cauca, from La Bota Caucana, specimen made from cultivation in 2018, *Anon. s.n.* (HPUJ).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Colombia.

Etymology: Named after Dr. Ruben Primitivo Sauleda, Orchidologist.

Notes: The species epithet *mejiae* is preoccupied in the genus *Zootrophion* Luer (*Zootrophion mejiae* Uribe Vélez & Sauleda, New World Orchid. Nomencl. Notes 129: 1. 2024), therefore, a new name is herein proposed.

Zygostates clarkei (Szlach., Lipińska & Skorowska) R.Kr.Singh & Sanje et Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Dipteranthus clarkei* Szlach., Lipińska & Skorowska, *Biodivers. Res. Conservation* 51: 1. 2018.

Holotype: Guyana, Potaro-Siparuni Region, *H.D. Clarke et al. 10137* (US-36663316).

Distribution: Endemic to Co-operative Republic of Guyana.

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